

Synthesis of ethyl(2Z)-2-(Aryl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-7-methyl-3-oxo-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-5H-[1,3]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate Derivatives as Biological and Antifungal Active Agents

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to synthesize several heterocyclic pyrimidine derivatives. Pyrimidine nucleus was synthesized by Pietro Biginelli reaction in past. There are two step reaction was carried out. (1) In first step reaction the derivative synthesized by reaction between ethylacetoacetate, substituted benzaldehyde, and thiourea. (2) In second step reaction give excellent yield of ethyl(2Z)-2-(Aryl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-7-methyl-3-oxo-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-5H-[1,3]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate derivatives (1-13) synthesized by using first reaction derivative, chloro acetic acid, sodium acetate, acetic anhydride, glacial acetic acid with various substituted benzaldehyde. The products have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against gram (+) positive and gram (-) negative bacteria.

Keywords: 2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro pyrimidine, Biginelli reaction, Antibacterial activity, Antifungal activity.

INTRODUCTION

Heterocyclic compounds have special attention in organic chemistry. Fused heterocyclic derivatives are of great biological interest, especially as antiviral, antitumor and antimicrobial agents [1-11]. Some of them derivatives exhibited modest activity against gram-positive and gram-negative strains. Thiazolo pyrimidine derivatives were tested for their anti-inflammatory activities. In our work on the synthesis of pyrimidine derivatives for biological evaluations, and moiety is described.

BIGINELLI REACTION:

A simple and direct method reported by Biginelli in 1893. Biginelli reaction is a multiple component reaction. In that ethyl acetoacetate, an aryl benzaldehyde, and thiourea are reacts and give thiourea derivatives. It is named for the chemist Pietro Biginelli.

In recent year heterocycles play a major role in drug synthesis. In that pyrimidine plays a significant role among other heterocycles. From literature survey thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine [12-16] and other derivatives considerable interest because of their pharmacological and therapeutic properties. Many of them have been found to have a wide spectrum of biological effects including antimicrobial, antitumor, antiviral, antiinfective, anticancer, antihypertensive, calcium channel blocker, and neuropeptide antagonist [17-18].

METHOD

Step: 1

Preparation of ethyl 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-2-thioxo-

1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate:

A mixture of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.1 mol), EAA (0.1 mol), and thiourea (0.1 mol) filled in 250 ml of RBF. Then reflux for 4-5 hr in presence of concentrated (HCl) hydrochloric acid as catalyst. After completion of the reaction, mixture was poured in water containing ice. Product was isolated, filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the pure compounds. The yield was 62 % with M. P. 166^o C.

Step: 2

Preparation of ethyl(2Z)-2-(Aryl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-7-methyl-3-oxo-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-5H-[1,3]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate:

A mixture of ethyl 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-2-thioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (0.005 mol), substituted benzaldehyde (0.05 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.05 mol), sodium acetate (0.05 mol), acetic anhydride (0.05 mol) and 10 ml glacial acetic acid taken in RBF. Reflux this mixture for 5 to 6 hr. Moiety was obtained by pours this solution in to cold water. Derivative recrystallized by ethanol. DMF: M. P. 225⁰ C, Yield 64 %.

ethyl(2Z)-2-benzylidene-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-7-methyl-3-oxo-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-5H-[1,3]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate-(1)

The purity of ethyl(2Z)-2-benzylidene-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-7-methyl-3-oxo-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-5H-[1,3]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate-(1) compound was routinely checked on TLC aluminum sheet silica gel 60 F₂₄₅ (E. Merck) using benzene-methanol (4.5:0.5 v/v) or benzene- CCl_4 -methanol (2.5:2.0:0.5 v/v) as irrigate and was developed in an iodine chamber. Other compounds of the series were prepared by using similar method. The purity of these derivatives was analyzed through melting point measurements.

Physical constants:

Where Ar = Different aryl group

Physical constants of ethyl (2Z)-2-(Aryl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-7-methyl-3-oxo-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-5H-[1,3]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate:

Sr No.	-Ar	MOLECULAR FORMULA	M. P. °C	YIELD (%)	% OF CARBON		% OF NITROGEN		MOLECUR WEIGHT
					FOUND	REQD.	FOUND	REQD.	
1	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	225 ⁰ C	64%	62.59	62.65	6.31	6.35	440.94
2	-4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	206 ⁰ C	59%	61.20	61.21	5.94	5.95	470.97
3	-2,4-(CL) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ Cl ₃ N ₂ O ₃ S	215 ⁰ C	62%	54.15	54.18	5.46	5.49	509.83
4	-4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	156 ⁰ C	63%	63.32	63.36	6.13	6.16	454.97
5	-4-F-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ClFN ₂ O ₃ S	181 ⁰ C	58%	60.15	60.19	6.05	6.10	458.93
6	-4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ BrClN ₂ O ₃ S	218 ⁰ C	59%	53.12	53.14	5.35	5.39	519.84
7	-4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	220 ⁰ C	54%	58.08	58.11	5.84	5.89	475.39
8	-3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	197 ⁰ C	61%	60.43	60.46	6.09	6.13	456.94
9	-4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	184 ⁰ C	60%	60.40	60.46	6.11	6.13	456.94
10	-3-OCH ₃ -4-OH-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₅ S	190 ⁰ C	59%	59.15	59.19	5.73	5.75	486.97
11	-2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₅ S	179 ⁰ C	54%	56.81	56.85	8.61	8.65	485.94
12	-3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₅ S	210 ⁰ C	59%	56.82	56.85	8.62	8.65	485.94
13	-4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₅ S	238 ⁰ C	56%	56.80	56.85	8.60	8.65	485.94

3d view of compound

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY:

Antibacterial and Antifungal activity:

The synthesized compounds were screened for their *in-vitro* antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia Coli* (Gram negative), *Staphylococcus Aureus* (Gram negative), *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram positive), *Streptococcus Pyogenes* (Gram positive) and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus clavatus* by measuring in MBC and in MFC method in $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The synthesized compounds were compared with standard antibacterial drugs Gentamycin, Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, Ciprofloxacin, Norfloxacin and antifungal drugs Nystatin and Griseofulvin. Antibacterial and antifungal activity was carried out by BROTH DILUTION METHOD at concentrations of 1000, 500, 250, 200, 125, 100, 62.5 [19] $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

Product Code	Minimal bactericidal concentration (MBC) in $\mu\text{g/ml}$				Minimal fungicidal concentration (MFC) in $\mu\text{g/ml}$		
	Gram negative bacteria		Gram positive bacteria		Fungus		
	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	<i>S.aureus</i>	<i>S.pyogenus</i>	<i>C.albicans</i>	<i>A.nigar</i>	<i>A.clavatus</i>
	MTCC 443	MTCC 1688	MTCC 96	MTCC 442	MTCC 227	MTCC 282	MTCC 1323
1	250	200	250	200	1000	500	500
2	125	100	125	200	250	250	1000
3	100	250	250	100	500	1000	500
4	125	62.5	200	200	250	250	250
5	250	62.5	200	250	500	1000	500
6	200	200	250	250	250	>1000	>1000
7	200	100	62.5	200	250	500	500
8	125	100	62.5	125	500	250	1000
9	100	200	100	62.5	500	250	500
10	100	200	62.5	100	500	250	>1000
11	200	100	100	125	>1000	>1000	500
12	200	62.5	100	125	500	250	1000
13	200	200	62.5	200	250	250	500
Gentamycin	0.05	1	0.25	0.5	--	--	--
Ampicillin	100	--	250	100	--	--	--
Chloramphenicol	50	50	50	50	--	--	--
Ciprofloxacin	25	25	50	50	--	--	--
Norfloxacin	10	10	10	10	--	--	---
Nystatin	--	--	--	--	100	100	100
Griseofulvin	--	--	--	--	500	100	100

DISCUSSION

Many derivatives of thiazolo pyrimidines are synthesized in research laboratory by me. There are many important used of them like anti-bacterial, anti-infective, and antimalarial activity. This thesis consists of the overall comparison of the compound synthesized in my research work. Out of them many derivatives possesses remarkable antimicrobial importance in research field. The purity of all the compounds was confirmed by their sharp melting points. Characterization of thiazolo derivatives will also record.

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REFERENCES

1. M. S. Al-Thebeiti, Synthesis of some new derivatives of thiazolo-[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3,5,7(2H)-trione of potential biological activity, *Boll. Chim. Farm.* 140, (2001) 221–223.
2. B. Tozkoparan, M. Ertan, P. Kelicen and R. Demirdamar, Synthesis and anti-inflammatory activities of some

- thiazolo-[3,2-a]pyrimidine derivatives, *Farmaco*, 54, (1999) 588–593.
3. M. S. A. El-Gaby, S. G. Abdel-Hamide, M. M. Ghorab and S. M. El-Sayed, Synthesis and anticancer activity in vitro of some new pyrimidines, *Acta Pharm.* 49, (1999) 149–158.
 4. C. G. Dave, D. R. Shah, G. K. Shah, P. S. Pandya, K. C. Dave and V. J. Patel, Pyridopyrimidines part III. Synthesis and analgesic activity of 4-aminopyrido-[2,3-d]pyrimidines, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 48, (1986) 75–77.
 5. K. Stulik and V. Pacakova, High performance liquid chromatography of biologically important pyrimidine derivatives with ultraviolet-voltametric-polarographic detection, *J. Chromatogr.* 1, (1983), 77–86.
 6. P. Zimmermann, J. Senn-Bilfinger, B. Kohl, G. Hanauer, S. Postius, W. Opferkuch and G. Grundler, Preparation of Imidazopyridazines for Control of Helicobacter Bacteria, *PCT Int. Appl. Wo 98 28, 299*, 2 Jul 1998; ref. *Chem. Abstr.* 129, (1998) 109095t.
 7. M. Bos, T. Godel, C. Riemer and A. Sleight, Sulfonamide for Treatment of Central Nervous Disorders, *Eur. Pat. Appl.* EP 815861, 7 Jan 1998; ref. *Chem. Abstr.* 128, (1998) 145382x.
 8. C. G. Dave, P. R. Shah, V. B. Desai and S. Srinivasan, Synthesis and biological activity of some pyridylthioureas and pyridopyrimidinethiones, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 44, (1982) 83–85.
 9. D. Bozsing, G. Kovanyi Lax, E. Berenyi Poldermann, K. Magyar, S. Tuboly and A. Mandi, Preparation and Testing of Aminoiminoheterocyclopyrimidines as Immunostimulants, *Ger. Offen. DE 3, 743, 935*, 14 Jul 1988; ref. *Chem. Abstr.* 110, (1989) 75547g.
 10. S. Shigeta, S. Mori, F. Watanabe, K. Takahashi, T. Nagata, N. Koike, T. Wakayama and M. Saneyoshi, Synthesis and antiherpes virus activities of 5-alkyl-2-thiopyrimidine nucleoside analogues, *Antivir. Chem. Chemother.* 13, (2002) 67–82.
 11. A. E. Rashad and M. A. Ali, Synthesis and antiviral screening of some thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine nucleosides, *Nucleosides, Nucleotides* 25, (2006) 17–28.
 12. B. B. Baldaniya M. M. Jotani, E. R. T. Tiekink, (2Z)-Ethyl 2-(2-acetoxybenzylidene)-7-methyl-3-oxo-5-phenyl-2,3-dihydro- 5H-1, 3 thiazolo-[3, 2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate., *Acta Cryst.*, E66(3), (2010), 762-763.
 13. M. M. Jotani, B. B. Baldaniya, Ethyl (2Z) 2-(2-chlorobenzylidene)-7 methyl-3-oxo-5-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-5H-1,3-thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-6-carboxylate. *Acta Cryst.*, E-63, (2007),1937- 1939.
 14. B. B. Baldaniya, M. M. Jotani, (2Z)-Ethyl 2-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-7 methyl-3-oxo-5-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-5h-1,3 thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-6-carboxylate.*Acta Cryst.*, E-62, (2006), 5871- 5873.
 15. B. B. Baldaniya, M. M. Jotani, J. P. Jasinski, (2Z)-Ethyl 2-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-7-methyl-3-oxo-5-phenyl-2,3-dihydro- 5H-1, 3 thiazolo-[3, 2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate. *Acta Cryst.*, E66(3), (2009), 599-600.
 16. B. B. Baldaniya, M. M. Jotani, (2Z)-Ethyl2-(3-methoxy-4-acetyloxybenzylidene)-7-methyl-3-oxo-5-phenyl-2,3-dihydro- 5H-1, 3 thiazolo-[3, 2-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate. *Indian J. Phys.*, 84(9), (2010), 1177-1182.
 17. K. S. Atwal, B. N. Swanson, S. E. Unger, D. M. Floyd, S. Moreland, A. Hedberg, B. C. O'Reilly, J. E. T. Corrie, *J. Med. Chem.*, 34, (1991), 806-811.
 18. C. O. Kappe, *Tetrahedron*, 49, (1993), 6937-7963.
 19. National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standard. Reference Method for broth dilution antifungal susceptibility testing of yeasts; Approved standard M27A2; (2002), NCCLS, Wayne, PA.

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